

HUMAN CAPACITY BUILDING AND HUMAN RESOURCES AS PANACEA FOR ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS OF SPORT TOURISM IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Sport tourism has been adjudged one of the money-spinning sectors that if properly harnessed is capable of creating jobs for the unemployed as well as increase the GDP of a country. However, in achieving this, there is need to develop human capacity building as well as providing a platform for training of personnel to actualize organizational effectiveness in sport tourism development in Imo state. The researcher discovered there is a lull in sport tourism development in Imo state and therefore suggested that training and re-training of workers should be key while competent and highly resourceful personnel be recruited to drive the sport tourism sector in Imo state to a logical conclusion.

Keywords: human capacity building, human resources, organizational effectiveness, Imo State

1. Introduction

Sport is a multi-dimensional concept with different meaning to many individuals in the society. To some it is merely a play while to others, it is ritual, yet to many more, it is just an entertainment and in recent time, it has added another dimension to its meaning, it is

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now viewed as a business venture (Ayeni, 2003). According to Morakinyo, (2000) sports has continually taken over the prime time and space in the electronics and print media and also occupies the subconscious mind of man to such an extent that man has become fanatically committed to the cause of sports, either as athletes, spectators or managers. He maintained that sports are a social phenomenon that has grown from its humble beginning of being an entertainment to a prominent business phenomenon that can no longer be ignored in the socio-political and economic structure of a nation. Similarly, sport tourism has become one of the biggest industry in terms of job creation and GDP growth of many countries of the world most especially the advanced countries and this informed why the industry is currently attracting big players from the private sector and as it were, such money spinning industry needs effectiveness in terms of organization most especially Imo state in particular.

In recent time, organizational effectiveness has gained interest in the non-profit sector during the nineties, thus non-profit organizations have realized that being critical of their performances is important to warrant the survival of their organizations. Therefore, these organizations are under continuous pressure to develop strategies and embrace management practices that would ensure organizational effectiveness. (Beech and Chadwick, 2004).

Consequently, organizational effectiveness in the contemporary world requires a great deal of managerial skill and expertise to manage the human resources and facilitate human capacity building of an organization for the sole purpose of achieving a set goal, and this informs while effective leadership is germane in the actualization of the development of sport tourism in Nigeria.

Parkhouse (2003) noted that achieving organizational effectiveness depends on commitment of top management leadership which is critical for diverse programme to succeed. Adedeji (2000) submitted that the complete delivery of sports tourism would be better achieved in the training and re-training of the workforce and effective management of the human resources. Similarly, Hinch and Higham (2005) inferred that for any organization to thrive in achieving its set goals there must be the motivation of the workforce through adequate training.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

In recent time, the concern for organizational effectiveness in the sport tourism industry has been emphasized. However, it is common knowledge that sport tourism in Nigeria is on the low ebb most especially Imo state as not many investors nor business men and even government at all levels are willing to invest due largely to unfriendly business environment and this may have been responsible for the lull being experienced in the sector.

2. Impact of Human Resources on Sport Tourism Development

Human resources management is the function within an organization that focuses on recruitment of, management of, and providing direction for the people who work in an organization. It is the organizational function that deals with issues related to people such as compensation, hiring, performance management, organization development, safety, wellness, benefits, employee motivation, communication, administration and training (Olajide and Ekpo, 2009). Thus, it is important to get the right people in the right positions in an organization to enhance effective job delivery in such an organization most importantly sports tourism sector.

Therefore, the quality of personnel in an organization to a large extent determines the level of effectiveness of such organization. Hence, human resources have been adjudged to be one of the greatest assets in an organization. According to Covell, Walker, Siciliano and Hess (2003), human resources in sports organization are of two categories; on-field which consists of athletes/players and off-field, which represents the employees who are actively engaged in administrative, managerial and service delivery components of the organization.

Hoye, Nicholson and Smith (2008) inferred that human resources management is strategic, integrated collection of employee-centered activities and processes whose objectives is to help the organization meet its short- and long-term goals. Research findings have revealed that human resources are critical to sports tourism development and must be effectively managed because it relies on the ability to explain and predict organizational behavior which is the attitudes and behaviors of individuals and groups in the organization, their satisfaction, commitment and performance. (Chen, 2007)

Consequently, in human resource management, individual and group factors interact with various organizational processes to affect the attitudes and behaviors of organization members. Organizational processes specific to human resources management include

- a) job design or the nature of the organizational tasks including variety, quantity, autonomy, interdependence;
- b) staffing and development;
- c) personnel evaluation;
- d) rewards;
- e) communication;
- f) leader behavior;
- g) power, including sources and uses of power and member involvement in decision making; and
- h) conflict resolution.

However, these processes are determined by the broader goals, structure, resources and culture of the organization.

3. Impact of Human Capacity Building on Sport Tourism Development

Organizations, in recent time functions in a globalized economic, technological and social environment: thus, every organization can function efficiently only if it has at its disposal the required resources in the form of facilities, equipment and capital while human resources include employees and their managers (Mshelia, 2001).

Consequently, managers and organizations are expected to consider three elements which are vital to their development and these elements are

- 1) precise goals to be achieved;
- 2) limited resources; and
- 3) people.

However, of the three, it is the entity of people that is most challenging to the managerial attention and that informs the need for human capacity building to enhance effective service delivery and good management decisions when it comes to sports tourism management. Therefore, management and more specifically empowerment of human resources in a particular working and social environment of an organization have greater importance than the management of other resources and require a meticulous attention.

According to Hoye, Nicholson and Smith (2008) human capacity building constitute for the organization a source of competitive advantage. They observed that other benefits of human capacity building to an organization include:

- 1) increased organizational effectiveness as indicated by higher profits, growth and expense control;
- 2) increased quality of service delivery;
- 3) improved employee commitment to their organization;
- 4) increased managerial effectiveness and innovation;
- 5) increased customer satisfaction within an organization;
- 6) improved cross-functional coordination;
- 7) increased emphasis on problem solving;
- 8) increased respect and trust among work units;
- 9) improved service quality; and
- 10) strategic implementation at the level of work unit.

4. Conclusion

Sports tourism is fundamental to the growth and development of a nation particularly, a state like Imo state in the South Eastern part of Nigeria that has produced great athlete recognized internationally. With this pedigree, it behooves on the state government to cash in on this by building its Human capacity effectively as well as re packaging the human resources department to ensure organizational effectiveness for sustainable sport tourism development in Imo state.

4.1 Suggestions

Base on the foregoing, the following suggestions are hereby made:

- 1) Training and re-training of workers should be the focal point of management if any meaningful development is to be achieved in terms of sport tourism development in Imo state.
- 2) Competent and highly resourceful personnel should be considered for employment as they will be able to drive the sport tourism sector in a way that will benefit the state in terms of wealth and job creation.

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